

A new proof of Smoryński's theorem

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Abstract. We prove: (1) the set of all Diophantine equations which have at most finitely many solutions in non-negative integers is not recursively enumerable, (2) the set of all Diophantine equations which have at most finitely many solutions in positive integers is not recursively enumerable, (3) the set of all Diophantine equations which have at most finitely many integer solutions is not recursively enumerable. Analogous theorems hold for Diophantine equations $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) = 0$, where $p \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$ and for every $i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$ the polynomial $D(x_1, \dots, x_p)$ involves a monomial \mathcal{M} with a non-zero coefficient such that x_i divides \mathcal{M} .

Key words and phrases: Diophantine equation which has at most finitely many solutions in non-negative integers, Diophantine equation which has at most finitely many solutions in positive integers, Diophantine equation which has at most finitely many integer solutions, Hilbert's Tenth Problem, Matiyasevich's theorem, recursively enumerable set, Smoryński's theorem.

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There is no algorithm to decide whether or not a given Diophantine equation has an integer solution ([2]). The same is true for solutions in non-negative integers and for solutions in positive integers ([2]). The set of all Diophantine equations which have at most finitely many solutions in non-negative integers is not recursively enumerable, see [3, p. 104, Corollary 1] and [4, p. 240]. Let \mathcal{E} denote the set of all Diophantine equations $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) = 0$ such that $p \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$ and the polynomial $D(x_1, \dots, x_p)$ truly depends on all the variables x_1, \dots, x_p . The last phrase means that for every $i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$ the polynomial $D(x_1, \dots, x_p)$ involves a monomial \mathcal{M} with a non-zero coefficient such that x_i divides \mathcal{M} .

Lemma 1. *A Diophantine equation $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) = 0$ has no solutions in non-negative integers x_1, \dots, x_p if and only if the equation $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) + 0 \cdot x_{p+1} = 0$ has at most finitely many solutions in non-negative integers x_1, \dots, x_{p+1} .*

Lemma 1a. *A Diophantine equation $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) = 0$ has no solutions in non-negative integers x_1, \dots, x_p if and only if the equation $(2x_{p+1} + 1) \cdot D(x_1, \dots, x_p) = 0$ has at most finitely many solutions in non-negative integers x_1, \dots, x_{p+1} .*

Lemma 2. A Diophantine equation $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) = 0$ has no solutions in positive integers x_1, \dots, x_p if and only if the equation $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) + 0 \cdot x_{p+1} = 0$ has at most finitely many solutions in positive integers x_1, \dots, x_{p+1} .

Lemma 2a. A Diophantine equation $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) = 0$ has no solutions in positive integers x_1, \dots, x_p if and only if the equation $(2x_{p+1} + 1) \cdot D(x_1, \dots, x_p) = 0$ has at most finitely many solutions in positive integers x_1, \dots, x_{p+1} .

Lemma 3. A Diophantine equation $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) = 0$ has no solutions in integers x_1, \dots, x_p if and only if the equation $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) + 0 \cdot x_{p+1} = 0$ has at most finitely many solutions in integers x_1, \dots, x_{p+1} .

Lemma 3a. A Diophantine equation $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) = 0$ has no solutions in integers x_1, \dots, x_p if and only if the equation $(2x_{p+1} + 1) \cdot D(x_1, \dots, x_p) = 0$ has at most finitely many solutions in integers x_1, \dots, x_{p+1} .

Lemma 4. If a polynomial $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) \in \mathbb{Z}[x_1, \dots, x_p]$ truly depends on all the variables x_1, \dots, x_p , then the polynomial $(2x_{p+1} + 1) \cdot D(x_1, \dots, x_p)$ truly depends on all the variables x_1, \dots, x_{p+1} .

Theorem 1. If the set of all Diophantine equations which have at most finitely many solutions in non-negative integers is recursively enumerable, then there exists an algorithm which decides whether or not a given Diophantine equation has a solution in non-negative integers.

Proof. Suppose that $\{\mathcal{S}_i = 0\}_{i=2}^{\infty}$ is a computable sequence of all Diophantine equations which have at most finitely many solutions in non-negative integers. The algorithm presented in Flowchart 1 uses a computable surjection from $\mathbb{N} \setminus \{0, 1\}$ onto \mathbb{N}^p . By this and Lemma 1, the execution of Flowchart 1 decides whether or not a Diophantine equation $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) = 0$ has a solution in non-negative integers.

Flowchart 1

□

Corollary 1. *By Matiyasevich's theorem, the set of all Diophantine equations which have at most finitely many solutions in non-negative integers is not recursively enumerable.*

The analogous reasoning with Lemmas 1a and 4 shows that the set of all equations from \mathcal{E} which have at most finitely many solutions in non-negative integers is not recursively enumerable.

Theorem 2. *If the set of all Diophantine equations which have at most finitely many solutions in positive integers is recursively enumerable, then there exists an algorithm which decides whether or not a given Diophantine equation has a solution in positive integers.*

Proof. Suppose that $\{\mathcal{T}_i = 0\}_{i=2}^{\infty}$ is a computable sequence of all Diophantine equations which have at most finitely many solutions in positive integers. The algorithm presented in Flowchart 2 uses a computable surjection from $\mathbb{N} \setminus \{0, 1\}$ onto $(\mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\})^p$. By this and Lemma 2, the execution of Flowchart 2 decides whether or not a Diophantine equation $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) = 0$ has a solution in positive integers.

Flowchart 2

□

Corollary 2. *By Matiyasevich's theorem, the set of all Diophantine equations which have at most finitely many solutions in positive integers is not recursively enumerable.*

The analogous reasoning with Lemmas 2a and 4 shows that the set of all equations from \mathcal{E} which have at most finitely many solutions in positive integers is not recursively enumerable.

Theorem 3. *If the set of all Diophantine equations which have at most finitely many integer solutions is recursively enumerable, then there exists an algorithm which decides whether or not a given Diophantine equation has an integer solution.*

Proof. Suppose that $\{\mathcal{U}_i = 0\}_{i=2}^{\infty}$ is a computable sequence of all Diophantine equations which have at most finitely many integer solutions. There are infinitely many prime numbers of the form $3k + 1$ and there are infinitely many prime numbers of the form $3k + 2$, see [1, p. 80]. Hence, the algorithm presented in Flowchart 3 uses a computable surjection from $\mathbb{N} \setminus \{0, 1\}$ onto \mathbb{Z}^p . By this and Lemma 3, the execution of Flowchart 3 decides whether or not a Diophantine equation $D(x_1, \dots, x_p) = 0$ has an integer solution.

Flowchart 3

□

Corollary 3. *By Matiyasevich's theorem, the set of all Diophantine equations which have at most finitely many integer solutions is not recursively enumerable.*

The analogous reasoning with Lemmas 3a and 4 shows that the set of all equations from \mathcal{E} which have at most finitely many integer solutions is not recursively enumerable.

References

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